

Reduction of nitroaromatics with a new heterogenised MCM-41-1-(benzimidazol-2-yl)ethanone thiosemicarbazone Pd^{II} complex

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The effectiveness of Pd complex anchored on MCM-41 was studied and the catalyst is used for the reduction of nitroaromatics by molecular hydrogen at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. The catalyst was reused for several cycles with consistent activity.

Catalytic hydrogenation and catalytic transfer hydrogenation¹ are the most common methods for the synthesis of aromatic amines by the reduction of nitro compounds. Many reducing agents have been used to reduce aromatic nitro compounds with the most classic being zinc, tin or iron in the presence of an acid². Most of the chemical methods are associated with long reaction times, high temperatures, high pressures and lack of chemoselectivity. Among all the catalysts palladium complexes and heterogenised Pd catalysts have proved to be fascinating systems for such reactions³. In view of this we wish to report a simple, convenient and efficient method for the reduction of nitroaromatics using a recyclable and eco-friendly catalyst. This method not only afforded the products in excellent yields but also avoids the problems associated with catalyst handling, safety and pollution.

Results and discussion

In this communication, we describe the effectiveness of Pd complex anchored on MCM-41 for the reduction of nitroaromatics by molecular hydrogen at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. The results are presented in Table 1. The ligand spectra showed two bands at 1275 and 750 cm⁻¹ which are shifted by 50–75 cm⁻¹ to lower frequency in the complex spectra. This indicates the change in the vibration of $\nu_{C=S}$ to C–S and confirms⁴ the formation of complex.

The reduction of nitroaromatics proceeds with high yield at atmospheric pressure and at room temperature. Dinitro compound is reduced selectively. The most important characteristic of our catalytic system is the reduction of the bulky molecule 1-nitronaphthalene in 98% yield with 3

Table 1. Reduction of nitroaromatics

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1		1	98	
2		2	98	
3		2	90	
4		2	95	
5		3	98	
6		2	95	
7		No reaction	6	
8		No reaction	6	
9		2	95	
10		2	98	
11		2	90	
12		2	95	
13		2.5	93	

h. simply by stirring at room temperature and also it is observed that in case of *p*-nitro and *o*-nitrophenol, the yield is improved, when compared to other catalytic system. The catalyst was reused for several cycles with constant activity without any reactivation. The resulting amino compounds were characterised by spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) data and by comparison with those of authentic samples and also by the mixed melting points with the authentic samples. Aniline IR : IR N–H stretchings observed at 3356, 1499, 753, 1621, 1277, 692, 1602, 1197, 504 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : aniline 2,6-*ortho* (¹H) = δ 6.52 (2H), 3,5-*meta* = δ 6.98 Hz, 4-*para* δ 6.52 (¹H), N–H δ 4.23.

Thus, the advantages of our catalytic system over others are : (i) it is simple; the reaction conditions are mild, i.e. atmospheric pressure and room temperature, (ii) easier work up, (iii) the catalyst is reusable, (iv) reduction of the bulky molecules was carried out simply eliminating the use of expensive reagents.

Experimental

Preparation of the catalyst : MCM-41⁵ was calcined at 550°C for overnight and refluxed with 1-(benzimidazol-2-yl)ethanone thiosemicarbazone Pd^{II} complex in methanol for overnight. After removal of methanol by evaporation the solid bright yellow coloured catalyst thus obtained was dried at 120°C.

Hydrogenation reactions : In a typical run the catalyst

(0.0057 g, 0.01 mmol of Pd catalyst) was suspended in 4 ml dry THF and treated with molecular hydrogen for 20 min and then a solution of the nitro compound (1 mmol) dissolved in 4 ml dry THF was added to it dropwise. A hydrogen balloon was fitted to the flask and resultant solutions was stirred at room temperature for the specified period (Table 1). The progress of the reaction was monitored through TLC. The reaction mixture was filtered, the solvent evaporated in vacuo and purified by column chromatography over silica gel. The reaction products were analysed by IR and ¹H NMR which were consonance with literature data.

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References

1. A. R. A. W. Johnstone, A. H. Willby and I. D. Entistle, *Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **85**, 129; N. Girenspon and E. Keinan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 3723; S. Rajagopal and A. F. Spatola, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **56**, 4481.
2. H. Alper and S. Amaratunga, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, **21**, 2603.
3. A. Zask and P. Helquist, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 1619; N. A. Cortese and R. F. Heck, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 3491.
4. K. Syamasundar and M. Adharvanachari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 32.
5. A. Tuel and S. Goniter, *Chem. Mater.*, 1996, **8**, 114.